

Admission control and end-to-end slicing for video streaming in MEC-empowered cellular networks

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Abstract—Cache- and network-agnostic Dynamic Adaptive Streaming over HTTP creates oscillation dynamics upon delivering mobile video content over cache- and slice-enabled data networks. In this paper, we bring to light the problem of user admission control, end-to-end slicing and video bitrate selection in next-generation 5G and Beyond 5G mobile data networks, where some minimum throughput guarantees can be provided for both the user-to-base-station and base-station-to-content-delivery-network links. Accordingly, we propose an exact algorithm to identify feasible bitrates and their minimum throughput requirements when the multi-access edge computing (MEC) cellular base stations has cached a known subset of video segments, potentially encoded at different resolutions, for a tagged video file. Simulation results provide valuable insights for user admission control, end-to-end slicing, video bitrate selection and caching in slice-enabled MEC-empowered cellular networks.

Index Terms—User admission control, end-to-end slicing, MEC, video streaming over HTTP, 5G networks

I. INTRODUCTION

Dynamic Adaptive Streaming over HTTP (DASH) is the de facto way for delivering mobile video content over the past decade [1]. DASH enables content providers to improve the Quality of Experience (QoE) of video consumers by adapting the video bitrate in response to the fluctuations of the wireless medium, e.g. due to obstacles or multi-path fading. DASH-compatible video streaming considers that the original video content is transcoded into files having different bitrates (i.e., resolutions) and that each file is partitioned into segments of equal playout time across all available bitrates. Accordingly, all video segments are stored at the Content Delivery Network (CDN) to enable the video player running at the mobile end user to switch to the most appropriate video bitrate in response to video content delivery delays and rebuffering events.

Network-agnostic DASH has been shown to sustain and even improve the users' QoE in pre-5G network deployments [2], where the radio resource schedulers at the cellular base stations admit and allocate resources on the basis of available resource blocks (i.e., frequency, time, power and space domains) and the available backhaul capacity. Nonetheless, an increasing body of recent works highlight that application-layer video bitrate adaptations by the end user side performs poorly when the underlying network infrastructure leverages edge network caching [3], [4], i.e., cache hits/misses mislead the video bitrate adaptation logic on the actual network status

causing "oscillation dynamics". Vice versa, performance gains of edge network caching are diminished if cache- and network-agnostic DASH is employed. Moving one step further, user-controlled DASH atop slice-enabled 5G and Beyond 5G (B5G) mobile data networks [5], [6], which can guarantee some minimum network-level Quality of Service (QoS) by dedicating heterogeneous communication, compute and storage resources along the end-to-end video delivery path, a.k.a., network slicing (NS), is a largely unexplored area [7]. Besides, the compatibility of existing video streaming over HTTP mechanisms with multi-access edge computing (MEC) and slice-enabled services is yet to be understood [8].

A vast amount of existing studies report that mobile video traffic is proliferated by massive requests for the same video content, making a very small portion of it to be highly popular. The survey in [9] highlights the value of fine-grained popularity prediction in cache-enabled networks and details the key video popularity prediction attributes that include static, temporal and social features. In our previous work in [10], we have addressed the problem of cooperative content caching in 5G network clusters composed by MEC-empowered BSs of different cache sizes, providing a zero-one multiple knapsack problem (ZOMKP) formulation and an exact dynamic programming (DP) algorithm to maximize the cluster-wide cache hit probability. The performance of random video caching (entire files) and multi-cast DASH in large-scale stochastic networks is investigated in [11], assuming that cache-enabled BSs store a single video. Aiming to minimize access times in Information Centric Networks (ICNs), Li et al. [12] formulate the problem of caching video segments at different bitrates as an Mixed Integer Linear Program (MILP), which is solved in polynomial time using greedy heuristics. In a more recent work [4], the authors bring to light the problem of oscillation dynamics created by DASH over ICNs and propose bitrate-based partitioning of available caches along the e2e caching paths, i.e., higher bitrates should be cached closer to end users (Ripple-based principle). Liotou et al. [13] propose a Knapsack formulation to adapt the video bitrate selection and radio resource management (RRM) on a per user and BS basis. The proposed formulation considers co-location of MEC servers with cellular BSs and an effective algorithm that decoupled the original problem into two sub-problems is proposed, i.e., multi-cell multi-user RRM and bitrate selection per segment.

The authors in [14] jointly investigate RRM, caching and transcoding of video segments to improve the QoE of DASH users in MEC-empowered 5G networks. A MINLP formulation that jointly optimizes cache and transcoding at the MEC server to align them with the RRM strategy of the cellular BS is presented, and a low complexity heuristic is proposed to solve it. The authors in [15] consider joint bitrate selection and RRM over slice-enabled vehicular networks and propose a slicing algorithm to cluster available vehicles into separate logical networks according to their channel quality. Lyapunov drift is employed to solve the joint vehicle RRM and video bitrate selection problem under probabilistic constraints regarding some minimum video playout duration per vehicle buffer. Joint RAN slicing and RRM are considered in [16], where joint scheduling of ultra-reliable low-latency communications (URLLC) and enhanced mobile broadband (eMBB) traffic is targeted for 5G networks. The authors provide a MINLP formulation that integrates power consumption and low-latency performance guarantees for the URLLC traffic as well as queuing latency and throughput constraints for eMBB under a common network utility function. Lyapunov optimization is used to break the original problem into two sub-problems, which are solved separately in a computationally efficient yet sub-optimal fashion.

Different from existing approaches, in this work we consider that the MEC-empowered cellular BSs cache a given subset of available segments, each encoded at potentially different video bitrates. We further focus on the problem of end-to-end network slicing and video bitrate selection in 5G/B5G mobile data networks that can provide specific rate guarantees for the the CDN-to-BS (backhaul) and BS-to-user links. Accordingly, we propose an exact algorithm of polynomial time to identify the minimum average throughput that the end-to-end CDN-to-BS and BS-to-user links should support to enable seamless video streaming over HTTP for a tagged video request, given knowledge on i) the availability of cached video segments per video bitrate, and ii) the maximum CDN-to-BS and BS-to-user capacity that can be reserved in an end-to-end fashion by the slice-enabled mobile data network. Valuable insights on how the proposed algorithm can be used for user admission control, end-to-end slicing and video bitrate selection is provided.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section II includes our system model and problem formulation. Section III presents the proposed algorithm. Performance assessment results and discussion on the application of the proposed algorithm in slice-enabled MEC-empowered mobile data networks are included in Section IV. Section V concludes our work.

II. SYSTEM MODEL AND PROBLEM FORMULATION

We focus on a video service request placed by mobile video user u to a tagged MEC-empowered cellular BS b that is part of a slice-enabled mobile data network and fetches non-cached content from a CDN residing in the far Internet. We consider that the video service request concerns a tagged video file f , which is available in Q different video bitrates at the CDN and is partitioned into S video segments. User u is considered

to request for a minimum video bitrate $q_{min} \in \{1, \dots, Q\}$ to meet its QoE budget, e.g., depending on the available video display, its preferences, or its accessibility requirements. Each video segment $f_{q,s}$, where $s \in \{1, \dots, S\}$ and $q \in \{1, \dots, Q\}$, is considered to have a prescribed video playout time of t_s seconds that is independent of the video bitrate used to encode the particular segment, i.e., we consider DASH-compatible video segmentation and consider a full video playout time $V = \sum_{s=1}^S t_s$ seconds. We also let $|f_{q,s}|$ denote the file size of segment $f_{q,s}$ in Mbits. We further consider that the video streaming over HTTP is performed at a fixed video bitrate.

Video streaming at a fixed rate enables the video player at the end user side to proactively place HTTP requests for all video segments to the MEC-empowered cellular BS proxy, enabling it to start downloading non-cached content from the CDN-to-BS link immediately while delivering both cached and non-cached content through the BS-to-user link. The aforementioned multi-segment video streaming over HTTP approach mitigates scenarios where reserved resources are under-utilized in the CDN-to-BS link when fetching cached content through the BS-to-user link, i.e., this leads to zero CDN-to-BS throughput. Such an approach is fully aligned with existing studies that report poor video streaming performance when DASH is used over cache- and slice-enabled mobile data networks [3], [4]. We also assume that the MEC-empowered cellular BS proxy employs a send-while-get (SWG) streaming logic to fully utilize the network resources reserved in the e2e CDN-to-user link. The SWG proxy logic reduces network response times and time-to-content by enabling the MEC-empowered cellular BS to immediately forward small chunks received from a non-cached video segment to the end user upon reception, i.e., without waiting to download the full video segment from the CDN before starting streaming it.

Without focusing on the particular caching logic followed by each MEC-empowered cellular BS of the slice-enabled network, we assume that the MEC-empowered cellular BS b hosts a limited subset of video segments from file f in its local cache and whenever necessary, to utilize the CDN-to-BS link capacity to fetch non-cached segments on-demand. Accordingly, we use the $Q \times S$ index array $\mathbf{X}_{b,f}$, which we consider to keep record of cached video segments from file f at the MEC-empowered cellular BS b , i.e., $\mathbf{X}_{b,f}(q, s) = 1$ if the video segment $f_{q,s}$ is cached, or $\mathbf{X}_{b,f}(q, s) = 0$ if not. We further focus on the scenario where the MEC-empowered cellular BS b can dedicate specific network resources across the BS-to-user and CDN-to-BS links, to guarantee an average network throughput of $R_{1,u}^q$ Mbps for the BS-to-user link and an average network throughput of $R_{2,u}^q$ Mbps for the CDN-to-user link. We use superscript q , provided that different target video bitrates have different average throughput requirements for the BS-to-user and CDN-to-BS links, depending on the video segments cached per video bitrate at the MEC-empowered cellular BS b .

The values of $R_{1,u}^q$ and $R_{2,u}^q$ are subject to optimization and their minimum values should be identified by the MEC-empowered cellular BS, taking into account the cache index

array $\mathbf{X}_{b,f}$, the target video bitrate $q \in \{1, \dots, Q\}$ and the residual capacity available in the CDN-to-BS and BS-to-user links, e.g., to allow service for a larger amount of end users. Depending on the status of the end-to-end links as well as the load offered by admitted users in the MEC-empowered cellular BS b , we consider a maximum capacity constraint $C_{1,u}$ for the BS-to-user link and a maximum capacity constraint $C_{2,u}$ for the CDN-to-BS link, i.e., the selected $R_{1,u}$ and $R_{2,u}$ values should not exceed that of $C_{1,u}$ Mbps and $C_{2,u}$ Mbps, respectively. Even though we do not focus on how the respective maximum capacity threshold are calculated, we note that $C_{1,u}$ can be potentially derived as the maximum capacity C_b supported by the MEC-empowered cellular BS for all users minus the sum of BS-to-user throughput necessary to support admitted users, i.e., $C_{1,u} = C_b - \sum_{k \neq u} R_{1,k}$. Similarly, $C_{2,u}$ can be derived by $C_{2,u} = \sum_{o \in \mathbf{O}} C_{b,o} - \sum_{k \neq u} R_{2,k}$, where \mathbf{O} is the set of outgoing links interconnecting the MEC-empowered cellular BS to the CDN, $C_{b,l}$ is the full network capacity per available link and $R_{2,u}$ with $k \neq u$ is the average throughput necessary for the support of admitted users. Fig. 1 provides an illustrative example of our system model.

We now formulate the problem where the MEC-empowered cellular BS seeks to identify the minimum average throughput requirements $R_{1,u}^q$ and $R_{2,u}^q$ for a given video bitrate $q \in \{q_{min}, \dots, Q\}$, while completely mitigating video stalls and guaranteeing an initial playback delay lower than D seconds, taking into account i) the cached video segments available locally (i.e., $\mathbf{X}_{b,f}(q, s)$), and ii) the capacity constraints $C_{1,u}$ and $C_{2,u}$ set for the admission of a new user in BS b .

MinRates(q): Minimum throughput $R_{1,u}^q$ and $R_{2,u}^q$ for a target video file f , video bitrate $q \in \{q_{min}, \dots, Q\}$ and user u .
Input: $[u, q, Q, S, V, \{t_s\}, \{|f_{q,s}|\}, \mathbf{X}_{b,f}, C_{1,u}, C_{2,u}, D]$

$$\begin{aligned} & \min R_{1,u}^q, R_{2,u}^q & (1) \\ \text{w.r.t. } & \frac{\mathbf{X}_{b,f}(q, 1) \cdot |f_{q,1}|}{D} \leq R_{1,u}^q & (2) \\ & \frac{\overline{\mathbf{X}_{b,f}(q, 1)} \cdot |f_{q,1}|}{D} \leq R_{2,u}^q & (3) \\ & \frac{\sum_{s=2}^{s'} |f_{q,s}|}{\sum_{s=1}^{s'-1} t_s} \leq R_{1,u}^q, \forall s' : 2 \leq s' \leq S & (4) \\ & \frac{\sum_{s=2}^{s'} \overline{\mathbf{X}_{b,f}(q, s)} \cdot |f_{q,s}|}{\sum_{s=1}^{s'-1} t_s} \leq \min(R_{1,u}^q, R_{2,u}^q), & (5) \\ & \forall s : 2 \leq s' \leq S & (5) \\ & R_{1,u}^q \leq C_{1,u}, R_{2,u}^q \leq C_{2,u}. & (6) \end{aligned}$$

By letting \bar{x} denote the complement of the binary variable $x \in \{0, 1\}$, Eqs. (2) and (3) constrain the initial playback delay not to exceed the target threshold of D seconds when the first video segment is cached, or not cached, respectively. Eqs. in (4) safeguard the timely delivery of both cached and non-cached video segments through the BS-to-user link, aiming to completely mitigate video stalls after the reception of segment 1. Eqs. in (5) safeguard the timely delivery of non-cached video segments $s \geq 2$ through both the CDN-to-BS and the

Fig. 1. System model and setup

BS-to-user links (end-to-end delivery). Eq. (6) constrains the $R_{1,u}^q$ and $R_{2,u}^q$ not to exceed the prescribed capacity thresholds $C_{b,1}$ and $C_{b,2}$. Problem formulation MinRates(q) provides a feasible solution (if any) on the minimum average throughput values of $R_{1,u}^q$ and $R_{2,u}^q$. If such a solution does not exist, the MEC-empowered cellular BS b should not admit the video streaming session of user u for file f at a fixed video bitrate q . Note that the MinRates(q) problem formulation can also be extended to identify the set of feasible video bitrates $\mathcal{Q} \subseteq \{q_{min}, \dots, Q\}$ that the MEC-empowered cellular BS can support along with the respective average throughput values $R_{1,u}^q$ and $R_{2,u}^q$ that minimize the throughput requirements for both the CDN-to-BS and BS-to-user links.

III. PROPOSED ALGORITHM

In this section, we provide Algorithm 1 that solves the MinRates(q) problem formulation in polynomial time. Step 4 initializes the values of $R_{1,u}^q$ and $R_{2,u}^q$ to -1 to enable easy verification when no feasible solution exists. When the first video segment is cached, steps 5-7 verify whether the initial playback delay constraint D can be met, considering direct delivery through the BS-to-user link (Eq. 2). When the first video segment is not cached, steps 8-10 verify whether the initial playback delay constraint can be met, considering end-to-end CDN-to-user delivery through the MEC-empowered BS using the SWG proxy logic. Steps 11 and 12 calculate the sum of file sizes for cached and non-cached video segments in $\{2, \dots, S\}$, respectively, while step 13 calculates the total video playout duration of segments 1 to $S - 1$. Steps 14-28 validate that the constraints of Eqs. (4)-(6) can be met. In more detail, the left hand of Eqs. (4) and (5) is calculated in steps 14 and 15 for a given s' , respectively, starting backwards from $s' = S$ to $s' = 2$. If the constraints of Eqs. (4) and (5) are not met for the specific value of $s' \in \{2, \dots, S\}$, its negative value is returned to allow easy verification of the event.

However, if the constraints are met for the segment interval $[2, s']$, the current throughput requirements $tR1$ and $tR2$ are compared to the previously recorded values of $R_{1,u}^q$ (steps 20-22) and $R_{2,u}^q$ (steps 23-25). If they are larger, the throughput requirements are increased as necessary. Due to steps 17-19, Eq. (c4) will always be met at steps 23-25, i.e., $R_{1,u}^q$ and $R_{2,u}^q$ will never exceed the capacity constraints $C_{b,1}$ and $C_{b,2}$, respectively. Depending on whether segment s' is cached (or

not), the value of cached (step 26), or non-cached file sizes (step 27), as well as the total video playout time available before starting playing segment s' (step 28) are decreased. Recall that the time available prior to starting playout video segment $s' > 1$ is given by the sum of video playout times of previous segments $s < s'$. Steps 30-32 evaluate whether the minimum throughput $R_{1,u}^q$ calculated in previous steps can attain the initial playback delay threshold D if a direct transfer of the cached video segment 1 through the BS-to-user link is necessary. If not cached, steps 33-35 evaluate if whether the end-to-end CDN-to-user link can support the transfer of segment 1 to the end user while mitigating video stalls.

Algorithm 1: Exact algorithm for **MinRates(q)** problem formulation

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1 Input:  $[q, Q, S, V, \{t_s\}, \{|f_{q,s}|\}, \mathbf{X}_{b,f}, C_{b,1}, C_{b,2}, D]$ 
2 Output:  $R_{1,u}^q, R_{2,u}^q$ 
3 Function: MinRatesAlg (Input)
4    $R_{1,u}^q = -1, R_{2,u}^q = -1;$ 
5   if  $X_{b,f}(q, 1) == 1$  &&  $|f_{q,1}|/D > C_{b,1}$  then
6     | return  $R_{1,u}^q, R_{2,u}^q;$ 
7   end
8   if  $X_{b,f}(q, 1) == 0$  &&  $|f_{q,1}|/D > \min(C_{b,1}, C_{b,2})$ 
9     | then
10    | return  $R_{1,u}^q, R_{2,u}^q;$ 
11  end
12   $cBits = \sum_{s=2}^S \mathbf{X}_{b,f}(q, s) \cdot |f_{q,s}|;$ 
13   $ncBits = \sum_{s=2}^S \bar{\mathbf{X}}_{b,f}(q, s) \cdot |f_{q,s}|;$ 
14   $pTime = \sum_{s=1}^{S-1} t_s;$ 
15  for  $s' = S$  to 2 do
16    |  $tR1 = (cBits + ncBits)/pTime;$ 
17    |  $tR2 = ncBits/pTime;$ 
18    | if  $tR1 > C_{b,1}$  OR  $tR2 > C_{b,2}$  then
19    |   | return  $R_{1,u}^q = -s', R_{2,u}^q = -s';$ 
20    | end
21    | if  $R_{1,u}^q < tR1$  then
22    |   |  $R_{1,u}^q = tR1;$ 
23    | end
24    | if  $R_{2,u}^q < tR2$  then
25    |   |  $R_{2,u}^q = tR2;$ 
26    | end
27    |  $cBits = cBits - \mathbf{X}_{b,f}(q, s') \cdot |f_{q,s'}|;$ 
28    |  $ncBits = ncBits - \bar{\mathbf{X}}_{b,f}(q, s') \cdot |f_{q,s'}|;$ 
29    |  $pTime = pTime - t_{s'};$ 
30  end
31  if  $X_{b,f}(q, 1) == 1$  &&  $|f_{q,1}|/D > R_{1,u}^q$  then
32  |  $R_{1,u}^q = |f_{q,1}|/D;$ 
33  end
34  if  $X_{b,f}(q, 1) == 0$  &&
35  |  $|f_{q,1}|/D > \min(R_{1,u}^q, R_{2,u}^q)$  then
36  |  $R_{2,u}^q = |f_{q,1}|/D;$ 
37  end

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Proposition 1. *The time complexity of Algorithm 1 is upper bounded by $O(S)$. Its memory requirements are given by $\Theta(1)$.*

Proof. Steps 11, 12, 13 as well as 14-29 dominate the time complexity of Algorithm 1. Each one of them scales linearly with the number of segments. That is $C + 4 \cdot (S - 1)$, which can be shown to be $O(S)$. With C we denote the number of fixed steps necessary. Note that we use $O(S)$ instead of $\Theta(S)$, given that Algorithm 1 can omit unnecessary computations using steps 6, 9 and 20, i.e., if the initial playback delay, or the video stall constraints, are not met. Provided that no arrays are used to support it, Algorithm 1 requires $\Theta(1)$ memory.

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS

To assess the performance of the proposed Algorithm 1, we employ the Big Buck Bunny (BBB) video [17] with an original resolution at 2160p, frame rate at 30 FPS and video playout duration $V = 634.6$ seconds. Using the FFmpeg software [18], we have transcoded the BBB video file into six resolutions and used the GPAC MP4 Box [19] to partition each video file into DASH-compatible video/audio segments of a video playout time $T = 10$ seconds, which resulted in 64 segments per resolution. Obviously, the last segment is 4.6 secs. The average e2e throughput required to transmit a full video file of a target resolution when no cache is available, can be calculated by the total file size in bits (not bytes) divided by the total video duration (634.6 seconds). For our dataset, the respective values are as follows: 9.18 Mbps for video streaming at 2160p, 5.28Mbps at 1440p, 3.48 Mbps at 1080p, 2.01 Mbps at 720p, 1.21 Mbps at 480p and 0.9 Mbps at 320p. The MP4Box has been used to create a helper manifest file, which serves as index and metadata holder for the generated segments. The video segments and manifest files are available in [20].

For our evaluations we derive $\mathbf{X}_{b,f}$ assuming random caching. To achieve this, we generate random permutations of all available video segments, which are scanned in sequence until the available cache size is filled, i.e., segments that do not fit are skipped. We further average out the bias introduced to the different outputs (permutations) of random caching by taking 1000 samples per plotted point, i.e., the results are averaged over roughly 1000 different caching index arrays $\mathbf{X}_{b,f}$. Note that the MEC-empowered cellular BS can fit all video segments of the BBB video if $L = 1800$ MBs.

In Fig. 2, we plot the minimum required throughput values $R_{1,u}^q$ and $R_{2,u}^q$ for all available video resolutions $q \in \{360p, 480p, 720p, 1080p, 1440p, 2140p\}$ and increasing available cache size L . The values of $C_{1,u}$ and $C_{2,u}$ are fixed to 20Mbps and 10Mbps, respectively. By observing $R_{1,u}^q$, we derive an interesting insight: an increase to the available cache size L does not lower the minimum average throughput requirement $R_{1,u}^q$ for the BS-to-user link. This can be readily explained by observing that the constraints in Eqs. (2) and (4) limit the minimum average throughput in values that meet the initial playback delay D and completely mitigate video stalls during the playout of video segments, respectively. These constraints translate to the need for successful transfer of video segment 1 in less than D seconds, transfer of video

Fig. 2. Minimum Required Throughput vs. Cache Size L

Fig. 4. Probability of feasible resolution vs. Cache Size L

Fig. 3. Maximum Resolution vs. Capacity Constraints

segment 2 in up to T seconds after receiving segment 1, transfer of video segment 3 by $2T$ seconds after receiving segment 1, and so on. We also observe that an increase of the available cache size L can greatly reduce the throughput requirements for the CDN-to-BS backhaul link $R_{2,u}^q$. Notably, Algorithm 1 can be readily used to infer on the optimal trade-off between storage and network resource usage given the cache index array $\mathbf{X}_{b,f}$ and the prescribed maximum capacity constraints $C_{1,u}/C_{2,u}$ that govern the end-to-end CDN-to-user links, while simultaneously guaranteeing complete mitigation of video stalls. Besides, Algorithm 1 can be leveraged to identify the maximum feasible video bitrate in view of the system constraints, by solving the $Minrate(q)$ problem for all video available resolutions. Such an example is shown in Fig. 2, where we observe that the video resolution 2160p is feasible only for $L \geq 100$ MBs.

In Fig. 3, we leverage Algorithm 1 to plot the maximum feasible video bitrate for specific values of L (legend) as

well as $C_{1,u}$ and $C_{2,u}$ (x-axis). For $C_{1,u} = 10$ Mbps and $C_{2,u} = 4$ Mbps (first triad), we observe that an increase of the cache size L from 0 to 100 (or 100 to 800), enables the MEC-empowered cellular BS to support the requested video service of user u at higher video bitrates. Although a similar trend is observed for $L = 0, 100$ MBs and $C_{1,u} = 10$ Mbps and $C_{2,u} = 8$ Mbps (second triad), we observe that the maximum feasible performance for $L = 800$ MBs does not further improve to 2160p, given that the available BS-to-user link capacity is low and inevitably leads to video stalls (i.e., some segments cannot be served on time). Thus, increasing the available cache size to very large values does not necessarily allow for the maximum available resolution to be attained if the BS-to-user capacity is not sufficient. Nonetheless, for $C_{1,u} = 20$ Mbps and $C_{2,u} = 8$ Mbps, the maximum available video bitrate of 2160p is achieved if a significant amount of cache size can be utilized, i.e., for $L = 800$ MBs. In this case, an enhanced utilization of the increased BS-to-user link capacity reserved is achieved.

Once again, Algorithm 1 can be readily used to identify the maximum feasible video bitrate for a given slice resource format, or to infer on the minimum required cache size/capacity link resources that should be dedicated to attain a specific video bitrate while completely mitigating video stalls and fully utilizing the reserved slice resources. Based on the aforementioned inference, Algorithm 1 enables the MEC-empowered BS to infer on which video requests it can serve, by avoiding the admission of users with a minimum video bitrate requirement q_{min} that is lower than the maximum feasible one. This video-aware user admission and slice control approach also enables inference on which particular video bitrates can be supported and at what cost, e.g., by taking into consideration the storage and network capacity costs per required unit; thus, enabling on-the-fly resource pricing and allocation of resources even to end users in emerging mobile data access with subscription-free mobile data access [21].

In Fig. 4, we shed more light on how probable is that a given video resolution will have a feasible solution, assuming random caching. We calculate the probability that a given resolution is feasible as the percentage of samples that do not return negative $R_{1,u}/R_{2,u}$ values as compared to the total number of samples examined per run (i.e., 1000). We firstly observe that for the given capacity constraints $C_{1,u} = 6\text{Mbps}$ and $C_{2,u} = 2\text{Mbps}$, the two lower video bitrates (480p/320p) are always feasible independent of the caching outcome. We also observe that, for the given $C_{1,u}/C_{2,u}$ values, the two higher video bitrates (2160p/1440p) are never feasible even if all segments are cached ($L = 1800\text{ MBs}$). Notably, for $q = 720p$ there exists at least one feasible caching index array (i.e., caching strategy) even for very low values of the cache size L ($\leq 100\text{MBs}$), highlighting that the employment of more sophisticated strategies can allow the MEC-empowered cellular BS to better utilize available resources by identifying the right sequence of cached and non-cached segments. For $L > 600\text{MBs}$, there exist feasible caching index arrays (codes) for video bitrate $q = 1080p$ as well. For $q = 720p$ and $q = 1080p$, we observe that the performance of random caching scales linearly with the available cache size. As part of our future work, we intend to identify optimal caching codes given specific throughput and storage capacity constraints.

V. CONCLUSION

In this work, we have formulated the problem of minimizing the average throughput requirements of mobile video streaming over HTTP for a tagged video file, video bitrate, end user, and cellular BS, which proactively caches video segments, potentially at different video bitrates. Assuming that non-cached segments are fetched by a CDN and that the slice-enabled mobile data network can provide some minimum performance guarantees for the user-to-BS and BS-to-CDN average throughput, we have proposed an exact polynomial time algorithm to infer on feasible video bitrates and their minimum throughput requirements in the end-to-end CDN-to-user path, while completely mitigating video stalls and constraining initial playback delay within acceptable thresholds. Simulation results have demonstrated that the BS-to-user minimum throughput requirements strongly depend on the selected video bitrate and the file size of video contents, being also independent of the the available cache size at the MEC-empowered BS. The proposed algorithm has been shown to readily infer on the optimal trade-off between backhaul link resource reservation (network slicing) and available cache size (storage), avoiding under-utilization of reserved resources while preserving the user QoE when mobile video streaming over HTTP is performed at a fixed video bitrate. As part of our future work, we intend to identify optimal caching codes given specific throughput and storage capacity constraints.

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REFERENCES

- [1] A. A. Barakabitze et al., "QoE Management of Multimedia Streaming Services in Future Networks: A Tutorial and Survey", *IEEE Commun. Surv. & Tut.*, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 526-565, Q1 2020.
- [2] A. Bentaleb et al., "A Survey on Bitrate Adaptation Schemes for Streaming Media Over HTTP", *IEEE Commun. Surv. & Tut.*, vol. 21, no. 1, pp. 562-585, Q1 2019.
- [3] D. H. Lee, C. Dovrolis, and A. C. Begen. "Caching in HTTP Adaptive Streaming: Friend or Foe?", *Proceedings of Network and Operating System Support on Digital Audio and Video Workshop (NOSSDAV '14)*, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 31–36.
- [4] W. Li et al., "Quality of Experience in ICN: Keep Your Low-Bitrate Close and High-Bitrate Closer", *IEEE/ACM Trans. on Netw.*, vol. 29, no. 2, pp. 557-570, April 2021.
- [5] 3GPP TS 38.300 V16.8.0, "NR; NR and NG-RAN Overall Description; Stage-2", *3GPP*, Technical Specification, Dec. 2021.
- [6] D. King et al., "FG-NET2030 – Focus Group on Technologies for Network 2030, Network 2030 - Terms and Definitions for Network 2030", *Standard. Sector of ITU*, Technical Specification, Jun 2020.
- [7] Q. Wang et al., "Enable Advanced QoS-Aware Network Slicing in 5G Networks for Slice-Based Media Use Cases", *IEEE Trans. on Broadcasting*, vol. 65, no. 2, pp. 444-453, June 2019.
- [8] A. Mehrabi, M. Siekkinen and A. Ylä-Jääski, "Edge Computing Assisted Adaptive Mobile Video Streaming", *IEEE Trans. on Mob. Comput.*, vol. 18, no. 4, pp. 787-800, 1 April 2019.
- [9] H. S. Goian et al., "Popularity-Based Video Caching Techniques for Cache-Enabled Networks: A Survey", *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 27699-27719, March 2019.
- [10] T. M. Ayenew, D. Xenakis, N. Passas and L. Merakos, "Cooperative Content Caching in MEC-Enabled Heterogeneous Cellular Networks", *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 98883-98903, July 2021.
- [11] D. Jiang et al., "Analysis and Optimization of Caching and Multicasting for Multi-Quality Videos in Large-Scale Wireless Networks", *IEEE Trans. on Comm.*, vol.67, no.7, pp.4913-4927, Jul 2019
- [12] W. Li et al., "Rate-Selective Caching for Adaptive Streaming Over Information-Centric Networks", *IEEE Trans. on Comput.*, vol. 66, no. 9, pp. 1613-1628, 1 Sept. 2017.
- [13] E. Liotou et al., "QoE-SDN APP: A Rate-guided QoE-aware SDN-APP for HTTP Adaptive Video Streaming", *IEEE J. on Sel. Areas in Commun.*, vol. 36, no. 3, pp. 598-615, March 2018.
- [14] X. Huang et al., "Towards 5G: Joint Optimization of Video Segment Caching, Transcoding and Resource Allocation for Adaptive Video Streaming in a Multi-Access Edge Computing Network", *IEEE Trans. on Vehic. Techn.*, vol.70, no.10, pp.10909-10924, Oct 2021
- [15] H. Khan et al., "Enhancing Video Streaming in Vehicular Networks via Resource Slicing", *IEEE Trans. on Vehic. Techn.*, vol.69, no.4, pp.3513-3522, Apr 2020
- [16] L. Feng et al., "Dynamic Resource Allocation With RAN Slicing and Scheduling for uRLLC and eMBB Hybrid Services", *IEEE Access*, vol.8, pp.34538-34551, 2020.
- [17] *Big Buck Bunny*, short computer-animated comedy film featuring animals of the forest, made by the Blender Institute, part of the Blender Foundation, 2008. [Online] peach.blender.org.
- [18] *FFmpeg*, suite of libraries and programs for handling video, audio, and other multimedia files and streams. [Online]: ffmpeg.org
- [19] J. Le Feuvre, "GPAC filters", Proceedings of the 11th ACM Multimedia Systems Conference, pp. 249-254, May 2020.
- [20] N. Episkopos and D. Xenakis, "Big Buck Bunny Video Segments", GitHub. [Online]: https://gain.di.uoa.gr/DASH/dash_segments_bbb.7z
- [21] D. Xenakis, A. Tsiota, C. Koullis, C. Xenakis and N. Passas, "Contractless Mobile Data Access Beyond 5G: Fully-decentralized, high-throughput and anonymous asset trading over the Blockchain", *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 73963-74016, 2021.